

The Selective Catalytic Hydrogenation of Polyunsaturated Organic Compounds

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It gives me great pleasure to join with Professor Ray's other friends in paying tribute to him. His work in Coordination Chemistry is among the best and excites the admiration of all of us. He has trained many students and they are now carrying on with research in several areas of chemistry. Thus, through his own research and that of his students, he has played an important role in the progress of Coordination Chemistry.

SOYBEANS constitute a major agricultural crop in many parts of the world, and a great deal of research has been done on soybean oil, which is the constituent of the greatest value. In the United States, at least, it is used mainly in foods such as oleomargarine, salad dressings and salad oils, so flavor and digestibility are important properties. This oil is a mixture of long chain glycerol esters, the main ones being

In a typical oil, the percentages of these substances are approximately, 9, 50, 27, 4, and 10 percent, respectively. Unfortunately, the linolenate ester has an undesirable flavor, and it is important that linolenate be changed to linoleate, which has a good flavor. If the oil is hydrogenated too fully, stearate is formed. This is undesirable, since the saturated esters are difficult to digest if eaten in too large amounts. Oleate esters are not as desirable as those of linoleate, but can be used if necessary.

This, then, is the problem with which the investigation described here was begun—to discover a way to reduce one double bond in linolenate, but leave the others unchanged, even though they occupy almost identical positions in the molecule. Several attempts had been made to do this before we began our work—a few of them with reasonable success¹. We have found that, by the use of a new catalyst, it is possible to get good results, but the positions which the double bonds occupy in the resulting molecule are not necessarily the same as those in the original material. Moreover, most of the double bonds which are not reduced assume the trans-configuration, although they had the cis-configuration in the original material.

The catalyst which we have used in this work was based upon work done by Cramer, Jenner, Lindsey and

Stolberg², who found that a mixture of chloroplatinic acid and tin(II) chloride is an active catalyst for the hydrogenation of ethylene, although chloroplatinic acid alone only is moderately active and tin chloride is not active at all. They showed, by X-ray studies and in other ways, that, in such a mixture, a platinum-tin bond is formed³. However, they did not study the mixed catalyst with regard to selectivity in the hydrogenation

of polyolefins. We found that, in a mixture of benzene and methanol, it brings about the hydrogenation of soybean methyl ester almost exclusively to the monoene stage⁴. In later work, we modified the catalyst to $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}_2 + \text{SnCl}_2$, which is actually the bimetallic complex $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{SnCl}_3)\text{Cl}$. We believe that, when hydrogenation is begun, this is converted to $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{SnCl}_3)\text{H}$, which is the actual catalyst. Although there is little knowledge of the mechanism of the catalytic reaction, we suggest the following ("MH" is used to represent the catalyst⁵)

The first step, according to this mechanism, is the formation of a π -bond between the platinum and one of the double bonds of the ester (III). This is quickly transformed into the σ -bonded compound (IV). This reaction is reversible. Alternatively, a very similar reaction may bring about the loss of a hydrogen atom from the carbon atom on the other side of M; this causes the double bond to appear in a new place in the molecule (V). Still another reaction which (IV) can undergo is the formation of a π -bond with an adjacent olefinic bond (VI). This forms a cycle which is readily attacked by hydrogen with breakage of the M-C σ -bond, but retention of the new π -bond. The process can be repeated until only one double bond remains; the cycle cannot then be formed, and the hydrogenation stops. Whether this mechanism is correct might be determined by the use of molecules properly labeled with deuterium. That it has some validity is indicated by the isolation of such molecules as (6)

catalyst. With palladium, the substitution of iodide or cyanide for chloride gives an excellent catalyst, even without the presence of tin chloride. The explanation for this is found in the fact that these ions, like the SnCl_3^- group, are both π -acceptors and σ -donors. Bis-triphenylphosphine nickel(II) chloride and bromide show little catalytic activity but the iodide is active and selective⁹. It is much less active than the platinum compound, however. Here, again, the addition of tin chloride does not enhance the catalytic activity.

Cramer, et al., found the $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 - \text{SnCl}_2$ mixture to be a good catalyst for the hydrogenation of ethylene, which contains only one double bond, but we have observed that it does not bring about the hydrogenation of a large molecule containing one double bond. Our platinum catalyst does effect the hydrogenation of short chain monoenes¹⁰ if the double bond is in a terminal position. This is shown in Table 1.

The small amounts of hydrogenation of the hydrocarbons containing nonterminal double bonds is attributed to migration to terminal positions. No experiments have been performed with long chain molecules containing terminal double bonds.

These considerations apply not only to soybean methyl ester, but are equally applicable to polyunsaturated hydrocarbons in general.

TABLE 1. CATALYTIC HYDROGENATION OF MONOENES WITH $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3 HRS.)

	1-isomer	cis	2-isomer	trans	3-isomer	Saturated Hydrocarbon
ethylene	0					100 (1 hr.)
propylene	66					34
1-butene	12.0			46.4		11.3
Cis-2-butene	0	71.1		27.3		1.6
trans-2-butene	0	9.8		89.6		0.6
1-pentene	11.6	30.2		47.2		11.6
2-pentene						
(mixed cis and trans)	3.0	27.7		67.5		1.8
1-hexene	12.5	28.5		41.6	5.6	12.0
2-hexene	No observable hydrogenation					
3-hexene	No observable hydrogenation					

The movement of the double bonds along the hydrocarbon chain takes place easily, so that even if two double bonds are distant from each other, they become conjugated and reduced⁷. Further work has shown that this catalyst can be modified in a number of ways without loss of its unique properties. Thus, platinum can be replaced by palladium, which gives a more active but thermally less stable catalyst⁸. A variety of phosphines can be used, one of the best being $\text{P}(\text{CH}_3)_2\phi$. Trimethylphosphine is a poor catalyst, however. Even triethyl phosphite is effective. Arsinides give excellent catalysts, but the stibines are not particularly active. The tin chloride can be replaced by lead or germanium chloride, giving catalysts which show some selectivity. However, they are quite inferior to those containing tin. In the original platinum catalyst, chloride can be replaced by bromide or iodide, with little change in the properties of the

turated hydrocarbons in general. The kinetics of the isomerization of 1,5-cyclooctadiene to the 1,3-isomer under conditions that do not bring about hydrogenation have been worked out⁶ and the hydrogenation of that product under more stringent conditions is easily effected.

Itatani and Bailar¹¹ have reported the isomerization and hydrogenation of a variety of hydrocarbons using four different catalysts—the usual $\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{SnCl}_3)\text{Cl}$, its palladium analog, dicyano-bis-triphenyl phosphine palladium, and diiodo-bis-triphenylphosphine nickel(II). The details of their paper need not be reported here, but two tables of data taken from it may be instructive. It will be seen from Table 2 that with 1,5-cyclooctadiene, the nickel complex is an active catalyst, and not only brings about isomerization and hydrogenation, but also the formation of fused, five member rings. The isomerization and hydrogenation of isoprene is

TABLE 2. REARRANGEMENT AND HYDROGENATION OF 1,5-CYCLOOCTADIENE (9.24 MMOL) WITH TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES (0.63 MMOLE IN 50 ML OF SOLVENT UNDER 55 Kg/cm² OF HYDROGEN

Run	Catalyst	Solvent	°C	Hr	Glc analysis				
1	Pt-Sn	CH ₃ COOH	90	1	56	44			
				5		100			
2		CH ₂ Cl ₂	90	5	39	61			
3		C ₆ H ₆ + CH ₃ OH ^a	90	5	97	3			
4	Pd-Sn	CH ₃ COOH	90	5	90	10			
5		C ₆ H ₆ + CH ₃ OH ^a	100	1	72	28			
				5	12	88			
6	Pd-CN	C ₆ H ₆ + CH ₃ OH ^a	100	1	79	6	14	1	
				5	30	14	47	9	
7		CH ₃ COOH	90	7	30	12	51	8	
8	Ni-I	CH ₃ COOH	100	4			2	67	31
9		CH ₃ COOH	90	4				86	14

^a Benzene and Methanol in the ratio of 3 : 2.TABLE 3. HYDROGENATION OF ISOPRENE (2.54 GRAMS, 37 MMOL) ; 0.63 MMOL OF CATALYST ; 50 ML OF SOLVENT ; 100°C ; 55 Kg/cm² OF H₂

Run	Catalyst	Solvent	Hr	Glc analysis				
				$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \\ \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \\ \text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \\ \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{C} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \\ \text{C}-\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \\ \text{C}-\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{C} \end{array}$
22	Pt-Sn	CH ₃ COOH + CH ₃ COCH ₃ (4 : 1)	1	80	5	2	9	4
			5	1	63	8	0	28
23	Pd-Sn	CH ₃ COOH	1	88	1		11	
			5	30	20	1	49	
24	Pd-CN	C ₆ H ₆ + CH ₃ OH (3 : 2)	1	79	18		3	
			5	12	64	11	12	1
25	Ni-I	CH ₃ COOH	5	100				
26	Ni-I	C ₆ H ₆ + CH ₃ OH (3 : 2)	22	10	53	29	6	2
27	Ni-I	CH ₃ COOH + CH ₃ COCH ₃ (4 : 1)	15	63	32	4	1	
28	Ni-I	C ₆ H ₆	22½	78	13	8	1	

shown in Table 3. It is evident that the nature of the solvent is important, and that for this reduction, the nickel complex is a poor catalyst.

Methanol, which was used as a solvent in most of this work, has donor properties, and thus it competes with the olefinic bond for a position in the coordination sphere of the platinum (or palladium). A search for a solvent which would dissolve the catalyst without coordinating with it unearthed the fact that methylene chloride, chloroform, and similar solvents, although they do not dissolve the catalyst, allow the hydrogenation reaction to proceed several times as fast as the benzene-methanol solvent^{1,2}. It is probable that, once the long chain olefinic material attaches itself to the catalyst, the complex so formed dissolves in the chlorinated solvent.

Eventually, the homogeneous catalyst was converted into a heterogeneous one by linking it to a polystyrene-divinylbenzene polymer^{1,3,14}.

In no case was the second reaction complete, but the majority of the diphenylpalladium groups combined with the polystyrene. In some cases, tin chloride was added; in other cases, not. The results of two experiments are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4. HYDROGENATION OF SOYBEAN METHYL ESTER WITH METAL-POLYMER CATALYST

		Temp. Time	Composition of Material				
			Saturate	Monoene	Diene	Conj. Diene	Triene
Run 1	Original Substrate Polymer (PtCl ₂) _{·508} + SnCl ₄	150°	14.2	22.3	56.2		7.0
		6 hrs.	13.8	26.6	39.2	18.4	2.0
Run 2	Polymer (PtCl ₂) _{·507} (no tin)	70° 3 hrs.	14.8	35.2	45.9		4.3

It can be seen that there is no marked change in the concentration of saturated material in either run. In Run 1, the concentration of triene is decreased by five percent, that of monoene is increased by four percent, and the amount of diene (both conjugated and non-conjugated) is increased by about one percent. Chemically, this is a good result, but it remains to be seen whether the product is readily digestible and has a good flavor.

In this short review, no attempt has been made to describe experimental procedures. These can be obtained from articles by Bailar and his colleagues in the research journals. The pertinent references, in addition to those already given, are listed in reference^{1,2}.

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